

Yuqorida keltirib o'tilgan omillar bolaning yuqori darajada ta'lim olishida namoyon bo'lishi uchun qo'shimcha tayyorgarlik ko'rish maslahati beriladi.

Aksariyat hollarda ota-onalar o'zlari "bolani maktabga borish vaqti keldi", yoki "yana biron yil o'ynab olsin", deb belgilaydi. Qoidaga ko'ra, ota-ona o'z farzandining sodda tajribalariga asoslangan holda, oldindan aniqlashga harakat qiladi. Muammoni bog'cha tarbiyachisi yoki o'qituvchi, ko'p hollarda esa uyda qarindoshlari, bilimdon qo'shnilar bilan muhokama qiladi. Va shunda bolani maktabga tayyorlashda uning bo'yi, og'irligi, o'qish va yozishga uquvi asosiy dalil bo'ladi.

Bolaning maktab ta'limiga psixologik tayyorgarligi hisobga olinmaydi, aniqlamaydi. Biroq aynan bolaning psixologik tayyorgarligi o'quv faoliyatining ichki tavsifnomasi sifatida o'quv motivi va bilishga bo'lgan qiziqishini shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

Bolalar ta'lim jarayonigacha o'z bilimi va o'yin orqali hosil bo'lgan ko'nikmalarni kattalar bilan munosabati va tasvirlar orqali namoyon etishi mumkin.

Bola stol yonida o'tirib rasm chizyapti. Ona bola chizgan rasmga qarab

"yana qandaydir bo'lmag'ur narsalarni chizyapsanmi?", kel yaxshisi kitob o'qiydiz, deydi. Bir qaraganda oddiy ko'rinishdagi vaziyat. Ona bola bilan muhimroq ish ustida shug'ullanmoqchi. Aslini olib qaraganda 3-4 yoshli bola uchun rasm oddiy qiziqish – o'yin emas. Bu bolaning psixik va shaxsiy rivojlanishi uchun qulay sharoit yaratuvchi, etakchi faoliyat. Demak, bolada o'yin vaziyatida yangi bilim va usullar harakatini ko'rish mumkin, u hali o'zi bilmagan narsalarni o'rganishga harakat qilmoqda.

Farzandingiz chizgan rasmga diqqat bilan qarang, nima chizganligi haqida gaplashing, imkoni boricha unga ko'proq savollar bering. Ko'proq diqqat va sabr-toqatni namoyon qiling, tasvirlangan predmet, gul, hayvonlar, qushlar va h.k haqida qo'shimcha ma'lumotlar bering.

Bu yoshdagi bola uchun diqqat barqarorligi tavsifli bo'lib, xotira faol rivojlanadi, so'z boyligi ortib boradi, fikrlashi rivojlanadi. Bola bu yoshda tashqi ko'rinishlarni umumlashtiradi, predmetlarni sifati bo'yicha birlashtiradi, ulardan foydalanishda harakat usullarini belgilaydi. Ular endi o'zlariga tanish bo'lgan vazifada sabab natijaviy aloqalarni tiklash qobiliyatiga ega bo'ladi. Eng muhimi, jismoniy rivojlanish tezlashadi. Sizning diqqat- e'tiboringiz muhim ahamiyatga ega. Axir bolalar kattalar kayfiyatiga nisbatan o'ta xissiyotli bo'ladi. Bunday murakkab mashg'ulot natijasini baholash qiyin, maktabda bu eng qulay holda yuzaga keladi. Bu yoshdagi bolalarning nutqi yaxshi shakllangan, tafakkuri rivojlangan bo'lib, muloqot qilish uquviga va qo'l yozuvi shakllangan bo'ladi. Albatta, bular shakllanishida sizning xatti-harakatingiz, ishtirokingiz katta ahamiyatga ega. Bu xatti-harakatlaringiz va ishtirokingiz bilan psixoprofilaktikaga yordam bergan bo'lasiz.

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BOTH CREATIVE AND TEACHER

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Annotation: In this article, a representative of modern literature and a pedagogue brief information about Elbek's work is given. Elbek's creativity in addition to being engaged, elementary school students and textbooks and training manuals created for teachers are cited.

Key words: parables, poems for children, collections, education manuals.

If we look at the past, we will enlighten our nation and our identity many of our creators and the works they have created are the eyes of many of us appears in front of us. One of our creators is modern literature representative is Elbek. Elbek's real name is Mashriq Yunusov, born in 1898. He lives in a farmer's family in the village of Xumson, Bo'stonliq district, Tashkentregion was born. Elbek despite his young age due to difficulties in his marriage, he came to

Tashkent and worked as a hired worker in many places. That's about it, in his epic «O'tmishim» he wrote:

Qarol bo'lib ishladim,
Bir burda non tishladim.
Turmushim kun-kun og'ir
Bo'ldi, yiqildim oxir...

During his 40-year life, Elbek wrote poems and epics, textbooks and manuals, wrote prose works and parables. «Elbek started the parable. Not through translation took the path of giving birth to parables. There is another person on this road has not been seen», - wrote literary critic Abdurahman Sa'diy.

Indeed, in the 20s and 30s of the last century, Elbek wrote «Maymunning qoziligi», «Jinning olov yoqishi», «Kampirning tovuqlari», «Ikki tulki», «Kuchsizlar dunyosi», «Yer bilan tog' o'rtasida», «Yelkan bilan kema», «Qora qushlar bilan toshbaqalar», «Ot bilan Odam», «Chumoli ila Chivin», «Quyruqsiz maymun», «Qaysi biri bo'ri» like different topics and different levels created parables. They have the ideas of fighting for rightness and justice pushed.

«Which in the parable of «one is a wolf», Elbek refers to the promises of the Bolsheviks about freedom and independence skepticism was expressed. Tsarist Russia is really Turkestan conquered and established the Wolf's violent attitude towards the Sheep. And the Bolsheviks, saying that they will save Turkestan from the tsarism, changed it had begun to understand the complexity of colonialism. Elbek, the same situation noticed and expressed figuratively in the example:

Bo'rimi yo aytgil endi kim vahshiy?
Outqarding sen meni bo'ri tishidan.
Hamda qo'rqinch shul o'limning vahmidan
Eng so'ng o'zing bo'ridan-da o'zdiriding,
Ko'rdim endi chin bo'ri ham sen o'zing!

Elbek wrote many funny poems for children. He announced in collections such as «Ko'zgu», «Yolqinlar», «Bahor», «G'unchalar». This to introduce children to nature in their poems, to insects, the Motherland in exchange for arousing feelings of love for plants and birds tried to teach the lesson of love.

Along with this work, Elbek also taught and wrote used textbooks in the course of his work. He writes about it like this:

«The problem cannot be solved by teaching from books alone. Maybe, ul to be able to animate the things written in the book and to understand what they have learned should be implemented. Of course, although there are few teachers for this work, should be looked at a work that shows the ways of learning like these books their forgiveness is touching. They were written for kazakh-kyrgyz schools with this wish in mind knowledge of this work accepted in primary schools that it is also used in Uzbek schools of the Pedagogical Commission of the Council

I fulfilled this task as he found me worthy and handed it over to me.» (September 1923)

Elbek for students of the 2nd-4th grade «Yozuv yo'llari» (1921), «O'rnak», «Go'zal yozg'ichlar» (1925) has created training manuals and collections. Folk art Bo'stanliq in 1921-22 in order to collect and study its materials district, and in 1932 to Ohangaron and Chirchik districts and Fergana organized an expedition to the valley. Elbek collected as a result of scientific trips widely used the materials in the «Bilim» collection for grades 1-3. «Ashulalar to'plami» (published 2 times in 1934-35), «Laparlar» and he published the collections «Ertaklar» (1935).

He considered Fitrat, who gave him the nickname Elbek, as his spiritual teacher and wrote the poem «Til» in response to his poem. He was accused of nationalism during the years of repression, and on August 7, 1937 was imprisoned as an «enemy of the people» and deprived of liberty for 12 years done. In 1938, he died of a serious illness in Magadan. However, his modest creativity is still with our students and teachers today serves as a special guide for.